

INJECTHEAL
INJECTABLE GEL FOR CHRONIC WOUNDS

At the Cattaneo Auditorium, “HEALing begins here: INJECTHEAL round table discussion on chronic wounds and patient-centered innovation”

Novara, 22/09/2025 – On Friday, September 26, 2025, from 11 a.m. to 12 p.m., the “G. Cattaneo” Auditorium (via Perrone 18, Novara) will host a public round table titled **“HEALing Starts Here: INJECTHEAL Roundtable on Chronic Wounds and Patient-Centered Innovation.”** The roundtable has been organised in the framework of the “First Consortium Meeting” of the [INJECTHEAL project](#), coordinated by Professor Lia Rimondini, Head of the Department of Health Sciences of the University of Eastern Piedmont.

The event will be attended by researchers, experts, and representatives of Italian and foreign institutions benefiting from the INJECTHEAL project, to discuss the research topic covered by the project, namely the development of new therapeutic approaches for the treatment of chronic wounds. Chronic wounds are still a significant clinical condition and affect a large percentage of the world's population (over 1%). This condition has a major impact on patients' quality of life and entails significant costs for healthcare systems.

Chronic wounds remain an ongoing challenge for medicine, as current treatment practices have significant limitations in terms of effectiveness, particularly in relation to controlling infections and inflammation and supporting tissue regeneration.

The aim of the INJECTHEAL project is to provide a concrete response to these shortcomings by developing a 4D injectable hydrogel designed for the targeted release of active ingredients into complex wounds and to support tissue regeneration processes, contributing to the reduction of inflammatory and infectious processes. The hydrogel will be developed using sustainable materials, with the aim of offering an advanced therapeutic option, particularly for “deep tunnel” wounds.

The round table will feature:

Menico Rizzi, Rector of the University of Piedmont

Ellie Lindsay, Officer of the Order of the British Empire, Honorary Professor, The College of Phlebology, London

Matteo Santin, Professor of Tissue Regeneration at the University of Brighton, UK

Mohammad Raoufi: Associate Senior Scientist at the University of Siegen, entrepreneur, and recognized expert in the field of CW

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Elham Sharifikolouei, Researcher at the Department of Health Sciences at University of Eastern Piedmont

Lia Rimondini, Director of DISS and coordinator of INJECTHEAL.

The event will be held in English and is open to the public.

PROJECT FACTSHEET

INJECTHEAL	
Project title	Multifunctional Self-Healing Injectable Hydrogel for Chronic Wound Healing and Tissue Regeneration
Acronym	INJECTHEAL
Start date	01 May 2025
End date	30 April 2028
Total cost	7 944 558.03 €
EU Funding	7 299 588.80 €
Coordinator	Università del Piemonte Orientale

OUR PARTNERS

Universities:

- [Università del Piemonte Orientale](#) (UPO), Italy
- [Universität Siegen](#) (US), Germany
- [Trinity College Dublin](#) (TCD), Ireland
- [University of Brighton](#) (UoB), UK
- [Politecnico di Torino](#) (POLITO), Italy
- [Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana](#) (SUPSI), Switzerland

Research Centres:

- [Joanneum Research Forschungsgesellschaft MbH](#) (JR), Austria
- [Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas – INGENIO](#) (INGE), Spain

SMEs:

- [EU CORE Consulting](#) (EUCORE), Italy
- [Akribes Biomedical GmbH](#) (AKR), Austria
- [Tissue Click Ltd.](#) (TC), UK

Charities:

- [The Lindsay Leg Club Foundation](#) (LCF), UK

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CONTACT US

Email: injectheal.eu.project@gmail.com

Project Coordinator: Lia Rimondini (lia.rimondini@med.uniupo.it)

Dissemination and Communication Manager: Irene Liverani (liverani@eucore.eu; info@eucore.eu)

FOLLOW US

Website: www.injectheal.eu

LinkedIn: @INJECTHEAL Project

Instagram: @injectheal.project

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